

Taiping 太平 Movement

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The Taiping Rebellion (1851-1864) was a Christian-inspired and cataclysmic millenarian uprising during the Qing dynasty that claimed the lives of between 20 to 40 million people. This entry takes a slightly broader view of the rebellion by examining the Taiping movement behind it from 1837 to 1866.// The Taiping movement can be said to have begun in 1837 when its founder, Hong Xiuquan 洪秀全 - a failed civil service examination candidate who belonged to the Hakka sub-ethnic minority in Guangdong - experienced a series of dreams in which he was taken to Heaven to meet the one true deity and emperor of China, the Heavenly Father. He was told that China had originally existed as a monotheistic utopia before Qinshi Huangdi and subsequent emperors had been seduced by Satan into worshipping heterodox traditions such as Buddhism and Daoism. The Heavenly Father further proclaimed Hong to be a "Heavenly King" (tianwang 天王) and charging him with restoring China to its utopian state as part of the transformation of the world into a new global order of Christian nations that would be united in their worship of the Heavenly Father and subordinate to China under Hong's rulership.// Understanding himself as Jesus' younger brother, Hong began preaching his new message and was driven out of his village to Thistle Mountain in Guangxi. There he became the leader of a religious group called the God Worshippers. The majority of its members were of the Hakka sub-ethnic minority. Literally meaning "guest people" (kejia 客家), Hakka were Han Chinese people who had been pushed out of the north by invasion and faced frequent conflict with the earlier Han Chinese settlers of Guangdong and Guangxi, known as the Bendi 本地, who resented their intrusion and pushed them to marginal lands. Hakka people formed the core of the Taiping movement and many of their practices, such as monogamy, mutual dependence, and a resistance to foot-binding, became features of the Taiping movement as a whole.// Between 1848 and 1849, Hong Xiuquan was absent from the God Worshippers. During that time, several shamans and spirit mediums, most notably Yang Xiuqing 楊秀清, became prominent within the group and initiated practices in which Jesus and the Heavenly Father would descend into spirit mediums and perform miracles such as speaking in tongues or faith healing. Although hesitant to endorse these practices, Hong did so upon his return and Yang Xiuqing acquired a place of prominence within the group as the voice of God.// The descents of Jesus and the Heavenly Father also resulted in iconoclastic attacks by the God Worshippers on local temples and other religious sites on Thistle Mountain, which intensified tensions between the God Worshippers and Bendi militias, resulting in numerous battles. Alarmed by the God Worshippers' clashes with the Bendi, Hong's denouncement of corrupt officials, and the loyalty of the God Worshippers to a transcendent deity over the emperor, the Qing state attacked them as a rebel threat in the winter of 1850.// Shortly thereafter, at the beginning of 1851, Hong Xiuquan proclaimed the inauguration of the Heavenly Kingdom of Great Peace and Equality (Taiping Tianguo 太平天國) and launched an all out rebellion against the Qing. The God Worshippers, now better referred to as the Taipings, invaded the central Yangzi river valley and succeeded in capturing the former imperial capital of Nanjing in 1853.// Hong proclaimed Nanjing to be the "New Jerusalem" and from it the Taiping movement created a theocratic state that, at its height in 1856, governed 30 million people. The Taipings were organized into specialty groups of 25 families that each provided a specific service for the state. Men and women, including spouses, lived separately and all property was held in common by the state through the institution of the Sacred Treasury. A particularly notable feature was the egalitarian treatment of men and women. Hong banned practices such as prostitution, concubinage, foot-binding, and widow suicide and insisted that women have equal access to

the military, government service, education, and property ownership.// Plans to reform the Taiping state into an even more utopian mode were cut short when, in 1856, Hong moved against Yang Xiuqing, who had come to refer to himself as "holy" and Hong as merely "eminent." Hong's attack on Yang Xiuqing resulted in the deaths of 20,000 people, ended the practice of mediumship, and fractured the Taiping movement, turning its commanders away from utopian visions and a united campaign against the Qing toward preserving their own regional power bases.// Despite efforts by Hong Ren'gan 洪仁玕, appointed prime minister by Hong Xiuquan in 1859, to reform the Taiping state according to a Protestant vision Christian material civilization, Hong increasingly reverted to the Confucian style of government that he had previously renounced. As Hong increasingly withdrew from government affairs, Qing troops besieged Nanjing, cutting off its food supply and eventually taking the city in 1864. Hong died at the same time, possibly by suicide, and the rebellion was declared put down that same year. Imperial mop-up operations continued, however, until 1866.// The Taiping movement's radical utopian vision and the devastating impact of its cataclysmic uprising left behind a complex legacy for late imperial and 20th-century China, foreshadowing and, in some instances, even helping to inspire the movements and uprisings of the 20th century.

Date Range: 1837 CE - 1866 CE

Region: Territory of the Taiping Movement

Region tags: China, Guangdong

Greatest extent of territory controlled by the Taiping Movement as well as their initial home of Thistle Mountain in Guiping.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping movement was a millenarian movement devoted to destroying "heterodox" (xie 邪) teachings and returning China to its pre-Confucian, monotheistic state. Accordingly, the Taipings launched a military uprising against the Qing dynasty in order to destroy all other religions and convert the populace to their own beliefs.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: Although the Taiping movement was violent and intolerant of other religious groups, it did incorporate a variety of beliefs and practices in addition to its flexible reworking of Christian theology. For instance, the Taipings claimed that China had originally been a monotheistic utopia that worshipped God, the Heavenly Father and that traces of this belief could be found

in Warring States (475-221 BCE) texts such as the Liji and Mozi (Bohr 2010, 376-377). More prominently, the Taipings also included folk practices of spirit possession and the use of mediums so that both God and Jesus were said to have repeatedly descended into spirit mediums on Thistle Mountain between 1848 and 1852 (Bohr 2010, 380-381; 384).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: The late Qing was beset by a number of different rebellions, some of which possessed religious dimensions. Because the Taiping movement focused its military efforts on destroying the Qing empire, it seems reasonable to say that they would have had some neutral contact with other rebel groups. That being said, the Taiping injunction to forcibly convert all people to their belief system means that conflict with other groups would have been inevitable had the movement not been defeated.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping rebellion (1851-1864) that was launched by the Taiping movement was one of the most cataclysmic millenarian uprisings and resulted in the deaths of 20-40 million people (Bohr 2010, 371). In addition to their battles with the Qing state, the Taipings maintained a high degree of violence against other religious traditions, actively massacring followers of Daoism and Buddhism (Bohr 2006, 112).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: The late Qing was beset by a number of different rebellions and so there was violent conflict outside the sample region. However, the Taiping movement did not engage in violence outside the sample region because the sample region was their territory. That being said, the Taiping injunction to forcibly convert all people to their belief system means that conflict with other groups would have been inevitable had the movement not been defeated.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: During its time in Thistle Mountain in Guangxi, the Taipings (then the God Worshippers) used baptism rituals to initiate new members that likely continued throughout the movement's existence. During these rituals, initiates would bow before two burn lamps and three cups of tea. They would then drink the tea and confess their sins. While water was poured over their heads they would vow "not to worship evil spirits, not to practice evil things, but to keep the heavenly commandments." They would then bathe in a stream and their names and confessions texts were burned to send the smoke up to the Heavenly Father (Bohr 2006, 107-108). It is important to note that the baptism ritual did not apply to those who were conquered and ruled by the Taiping movement without actively converting to it.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Personal choice was, of course, not always free, particularly for those living in the cities conquered by the Taipings.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Hong founded the Taiping movement through preaching and proselytizing (Bohr 2006, 104). As time wore on, proselytizing became increasingly coercive. For example, the descents of Jesus and God that began 1848 led to iconoclastic attacks by the God Worshipers on local temples in Thistle Mountain (Bohr 2010, 380-381). In 1851, this transitioned into a full rebellion against the Qing empire designed to restore monotheism to China. The Taipings conquered numerous cities, massacred adherents to other religions such as Daoism and Buddhism, and demolished religious sites (Bohr 2006, 112).

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– Yes

Notes: Because the Taiping movement was able to monopolize the resources in the areas it controlled, it can be said to have exerted an informal economic pressure on those present in those territories to convert to the movement and so gain access to those resources. This situation was typical of the late Qing, when weakening state power allowed various local groups (ranging from bandits to rebels) to control the resources of different areas nominally under Qing control.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Taiping movement actively warred with the Qing state during the Taiping Rebellion (1851–64). It was destroyed by the Qing in 1864, though imperial mop-up operations continued until 1866 (Bohr 2010, 387). The Taiping movement can also be thought of as a political movement and they were able to establish a theocratic state (the "Heavenly Kingdom of Great Peace and Equality" Taiping Tianguo 太平天國), but they never received political support from another polity (Bohr 2006, 93).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: A central tenet of the Taipings' faith was that China had originally existed as a utopian, Christian state ruled by its true emperor, God the Heavenly Father. This state declined because Confucius suppressed the true message of the Heavenly Father in his editing of the five classics and because Satan (the "old serpent-Devil") had led the First Emperor of China (Qinshi Huangdi) and his successors into following heretical traditions such as Buddhism and Daoism. Satan had even led the rulers of China to usurp God's title by calling themselves "emperor" (huangdi 皇帝). Consequently, the Taipings defined all those living in China who did not adhere to their faith as hereditary apostates and their uprising against the Qing was intended to end China's state of widespread apostasy and restore its lost golden age (Bohr 2006, 99-100; Bohr 2010, 376-377). The sub-questions below are answered with this broader understanding of apostasy in mind.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping rebellion, in general, was understood as a means of punishing and converting apostates.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

Notes: This occurred primarily through the conquest of cities and towns.

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are physically marked as such (e.g. branding, mutilation):

– No

↳ Apostates are executed:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are publicly executed:

– Yes

↳ Other corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Those who did not convert to the Taiping faith would be damned for all eternity in Hell.

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

Notes: This is particularly the case when one considers that the violence of the Taiping movement was believed to be a punishment by the Heavenly Father directed at the apostates of the Qing empire.

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: The Taipings considered themselves to be agents of the Heavenly Father's punishment against the apostate Qing empire.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 30000000

Notes: At its height in 1856, the Taiping movement ruled a 300-mile stretch of the lower Yangzi river valley from present-day Wuhan to the coast. It was ruled from its capital of Nanjing and encompassed a population of some 30 million people (Bohr 2006, 115).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Notes: It is important to emphasize that "small" here is intended as a relative term. The Taiping movement eventually ruled a territory of 30 million and was able to field armies of 1 million soldiers (Bohr 2006, 115). Moreover, it was not persecuted by a larger religious group, but by the Manchu Qing state. However, the Qing state itself had a religious dimension due to the emperor's ritual position as Son of Heaven.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The leader of the Taiping movement was the messianic figure of Hong Xiuquan, the so-called younger brother of Jesus chosen by God to restore China to monotheism. Hong also appointed five other "brother kings" to lead the movement, each of whom would come to maintain their own separate court (Bohr 2010, 381-382). These brother kings included Yang Xiuqing 楊秀清, the spirit medium who rose to prominence in the movement between 1848-1849 and who was considered God's voice (Bohr 2010, 380, 385). In addition to these high-ranking leaders, the Taipings were intended to become divided into "congregations" of 25 families, each of which was presided over a "sergeant," a position that was both political and religious. Each sergeant would be appointed directly by Hong Xiuquan. However, this plan does not seem to have come to fruition, though the Taipings did maintain bureaucratic structures and even civil service examinations following their conquest of Nanjing (Bohr 2006, 115).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: The five brother kings can be considered regional leaders appointed by Hong Xiuquan.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Hong Xiuquan was the leader of the Taiping movement and he assassinated Yang Xiuqing and 20,000 members of his court when the latter attempted to displace his position of preeminence (Bohr 2010, 385).

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– I don't know

Notes: There were at least two such levels (Hong Xiuquan being the highest, followed by his five brother kings), but the subsequent levels of the group's hierarchy are less clear.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: There are accounts of miraculous feats performed by Jesus and the Heavenly Father during their descents into the spirit mediums of Yang Xiuqing and Xiao Chaogui that included faith-healing, dream interpretation, and speaking in tongues (Bohr 2010, 380). However, these appear to have been confined cases and religious leaders in general, including even Hong Xiuquan, were not thought to possess supernatural powers.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: This point applies only to Hong Xiuquan who declared his son, the "Junior Lord," to be the grandson of the Heavenly Father and Hong's heir (Bohr 2010, 383).

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: This point applies only to Hong Xiuquan whose status as leader of the Taiping movement was due to his 1837 sequence of dreams in which he was taken to Heaven to meet God and declared by the Heavenly Father to be a "Heavenly King" (tianwang 天王) tasked with returning the world to monotheism by "beheading the heterodox [xie 邪], preserving the orthodox [zheng 正], and "relieving the people's distress" (Bohr 2006, 99-100).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping movement drew upon a number of different Chinese Christian writings, such as "Good Words to Admonish the Age" (Quanshi liangyan 勸世良言) published by Liang Fa 梁發 in 1832 (Bohr 2006, 95). As well, Hong Xiuquan saw evidence of China's Christian past in classics of the Warring States period (475-221 BCE) such as the Mozi and the Liji (Bohr 2006, 102-103). However, the primary scripture of the movement was the Taiping Bible, which consisted of six Old Testament books and the entirety of the New Testament. Both Testaments included passages altered and rewritten by Hong himself. In addition, the Taiping Bible included a third, "True Testament," which chronicled the descents of the Heavenly Father and Jesus in Guangxi between 1848 and 1852 (Bohr 2006, 115).

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Scriptural interpretation was completely monopolized by Hong Xiuquan himself.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Those in charge of congregations could transmit the scriptures edited and created by Hong Xiuquan.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: As it conquered more territory, the Taiping movement used existing structures and built new ones for use as churches and other sacred spaces. Examples of these spaces can be found at the Historical Museum of the Taiping Heavenly Kingdom in Nanjing:
<http://www.njmuseumadmin.com/en/Stadium/index/id/8>.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Examples of Taiping religious architecture can be found at the Historical Museum of the Taiping Heavenly Kingdom in Nanjing: <http://www.njmuseumadmin.com/en/Stadium/index/id/8>.

↳ Tombs:

– I don't know

↳ Cemeteries:

– I don't know

↳ Temples:

– I don't know

↳ Altars:

– I don't know

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: A notable example of a devotional marker were the large stones inscribed with the ten commandments that were set up in Nanjing following the Taiping conquest.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– I don't know

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Palaces

Notes: Each of the five Heavenly Kings of the Taiping movement had their own palace in Nanjing following the Taiping conquest.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: During their initial residency on Thistle Mountain, the Taipings were strongly iconoclastic. The God Worshipers (as the Taipings were known during their residence on Thistle Mountain) even attacked other locations in the mountains, destroying "ancestral tablets, religious images, and temples, whether devoted to ancestor worship, state Confucianism, or local Thistle Mountain cults glorifying such local themes as illicit love, matricide, or Zhuang dog worship" (Bohr 2010, 380-381). Despite this iconoclastic element, however, the Taiping movement did make use of iconography, particularly after its conquest of Nanjing. Taiping iconography was widespread in Nanjing and in a variety of locations along the Yangzi River. A notable feature of it is the use of character inscriptions. Examples of Taiping iconography can be found at the Historical Museum of Taiping Heavenly Kingdom in Nanjing: <http://www.njmuseumadmin.com/en/Stadium/index/id/8>.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– I don't know

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– I don't know

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– I don't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– I don't know

Notes: It is worth mentioning that, because the Taiping movement rejected the doctrine of Trinitarianism, it did not make use of the crucifixion imagery common to other Christian groups.

↳ Humans:

– I don't know

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Taiping iconography included character inscriptions.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: At the very least, Taiping paintings include a focus on environmental features and Taiping sacred sites were placed all along the Yangzi River.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The Taipings followed a Christian conception of the soul as an immaterial and immortal inhabitant of the body that would be rewarded in Heaven or punished in Hell after death. Although

less clear, a similar sense of the spirit would appear to underlay the Taipings' medium-practices as Xiao Chaogui 蕭朝貴 used Yao 瑤族 spirit journey practices to reenact Hong's ascent into Heaven during his 1837 dream sequence (Bohr 2010, 380).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife was divided into Heaven and Hell, which were thought of as occupying above and below spaces respectively.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Virtuous and worthy souls were rewarded in Heaven, which was ruled over by God and his eldest son, Jesus. It was thought of as a paradise of eternal joy composed of 33 different levels (Bohr 2006, 112).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

Notes: Sinful and unworthy souls were punished in Hell, a place of eternal torment inhabited by Satan and demons and composed of at least 18 different layers (Bohr 2006, 108).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: Reincarnation restricted to Hong Xiuquan

Notes: In general, reincarnation does not seem to have been a major belief of the Taiping movement. The exception to this, however, is that following the Taiping conquest of Nanjing in 1853, Hong Xiuquan declared that he was the reincarnation of Melchizedek, the messianic founder of Jerusalem who is described in Genesis 14:18 as "priest of God Most High." Although Hong disavowed his own divinity, his claim to be the reincarnation of Melchizedek elevated his status above that of Jesus because Hong claimed that, as Melchizedek, he had had "foreknowledge of the Heavenly Father's descent into Egypt and Guangxi and of Jesus' birth into Abraham's lineage" (Bohr 2006, 112).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– I don't know

↳ In cemetery:
– I don't know

↳ Family tomb-crypt:
– I don't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
– I don't know

↳ Other formal burial type:
– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:
– Yes

Notes: The Taiping movement was monotheistic and dedicated to the worship of the "Heavenly Father," a version of the Christian God described as omniscient, omnipotent, and omnipresent, but also fully anthropomorphic. He was at once the transcendent creator of the universe and the true emperor of China who chose Hong Xiuquan to restore the world to monotheism and recreate China's lost utopian age.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– Yes

Notes: In contrast to the insistence of Christian missionaries that God was immaterial, the Taiping movement understood the Heavenly Father in a fully anthropomorphized

sense as an old man with blonde hair and a beard who wore a black robe. He also had wives, children (such as Hong Xiuquan and Jesus), and was grandfather to Hong's son, the "Junior Lord" (Bohr 2010, 383).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Although omnipotent and omnipresent, God was particularly associated with the sky and was said to reside in the 33 levels of Heaven (Bohr 2006, 99-100; 112).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The Heavenly Father was not considered synonymous with the Qing emperor (the Xianfeng emperor) because the latter was considered the apostate heir to a legacy of heresy and usurpation (Bohr 2006, 112). However, there was some fusion of the concepts of monarch and God as the Heavenly Father was considered the true emperor of China, with all mortal rulers being considered merely "kings" (Bohr 2010, 383; 377).

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: God was considered Hong Xiuquan's father and grandfather to Hong Xiuquan's son, the "Junior Lord" (Bohr 2006, 113).

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Omniscient, omnipotent, omnipresent, not Trinitarian

Notes: The Heavenly Father is described omniscient, omnipotent, omnipresent, unchanging, eternal, merciful, just and benevolent. As well, he is not Trinitarian, but is, instead, a singular figure (Jesus is understood only as his son) (Bohr 2006, 113; Bohr

2010, 389-390).

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Everything on Earth and beyond

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: As the instrument of God's will on Earth, the Taiping movement itself may be regarded as evidence of the Heavenly Father's indirect causal efficacy.

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Heavenly Father is a benevolent figure who loves all people equally (Bohr 2010, 383-384).

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Heavenly Father is described as feeling anger, particularly in response to the failure of people in China to acknowledge and worship him (Bohr 2006, 100).

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Omniscient, omnipotent, omnipresent, not Trinitarian
 - Notes: The Heavenly Father is described omniscient, omnipotent, omnipresent, unchanging, eternal, merciful, just and benevolent. As well, he is not Trinitarian, but is, instead, a singular figure (Jesus is understood only as his son) (Bohr 2006, 113; Bohr

2010, 389-390).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The most notable instance of this is Hong Xiuquan's sequence of dreams in 1837 in which he was taken to Heaven to meet God and declared by the Heavenly Father to be a "Heavenly King" (tianwang 天王) tasked with returning the world to monotheism by "beheading the heterodox [xie 邪], preserving the orthodox [zheng 正]," and "relieving the people's distress" (Bohr 2006, 99-100).

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Between the winter of 1848 and the summer of 1849, Hong Xiuquan was absent from the God Worshippers. During that time, two shamans rose to leadership positions within the community. These two were "Yang Xiuqing 楊秀清 (d. 1856), the illiterate boss of the local charcoal-workers who practiced Hakka spirit possession in the name of the Trinity, and Xiao Chaogui 蕭朝貴 (d. 1851), Hong's brother-in-law and a tenant farmer who employed local Yao 瑤 族 spirit journey rituals to re-enact Hong's 1837 dream" (Bohr 2010, 380). The two acted as mediums that allowed for frequent descents of the Heavenly Father and Jesus, who communicated with the God Worshippers by possessing the two mediums and performed a number of miracles including "faith healing, dream interpretation, and speaking in tongues" (Bohr 2010, 380). Although Hong was uneasy about incorporating the practices, this more ecstatic form of religious experience remained a crucial part of the Taiping movement until 1856. In the intervening time, Yang Xiuqing became increasingly powerful within the movement, becoming known as God's "golden mouth" and maintaining a spy network throughout Nanjing after its conquest (Bohr 2010, 385). Eventually, Yang began proclaiming himself "holy" and Hong merely "eminent." In response, Hong ordered the assassination of Yang, along with 20,000 members of his court, on September 2, 1856. This act not only brought an end to the Taipings' medium practices. It also precipitated their defeat by the Qing in 1864 (Bohr 2010, 385).

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Although the Heavenly Father is not described as communicating through divination practices, Hong Xiuquan is said to have used prognostication techniques to determine the weather (Bohr 2006, 109; Bohr

2010, 380).

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The Heavenly Father's communicative dreams were given only to Hong Xiuquan and his descents into the Guangxi hills were conducted through mediums.

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

Notes: Whether this question is answered "yes" or "no" depends on the monarch in question. It is "no" if "monarch" refers to the Qing emperor, who was considered an apostate enemy of the Taiping movement. However, Hong Xiuquan was also considered a monarch, and he monopolized communication from the Heavenly Father, particularly after the assassination of Yang Xiuqing.

– No

Notes: Whether this question is answered "yes" or "no" depends on the monarch in question. It is "no" if "monarch" refers to the Qing emperor, who was considered an apostate enemy of the Taiping movement. However, Hong Xiuquan was also considered a monarch, and he monopolized communication from the Heavenly Father, particularly after the assassination of Yang Xiuqing.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Human souls are immortal and travel to the afterlife (either Heaven or Hell) when they die. However, although they are present in the afterlife, they are largely isolated from the living and are not thought to interact with them.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Notes: Unclear if spirits can observe the mortal world from Heaven or Hell and, if they could, how much they would be able to see and know.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Those souls that are judged worthy reside in Heaven, which is a paradise of eternal joy.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Those souls that are judged unworthy are condemned to suffer in Hell, which is a place of eternal torment.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Reward in Heaven or punishment in Hell

Notes: All deceased humans are judged by God and rewarded in Heaven or punished in Hell according what sins they committed during their mortal lives and whether or not they believed in, and practiced a belief in, the one true God.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

Notes: The Christian underpinnings of Taiping theology would seem to preclude the possibility that human spirits communicate with the living because they remained isolated in Heaven or Hell after death. However, Hakka beliefs did include the idea that ancestors could communicate with the living, but it is unclear to what extent such beliefs persisted within the Taiping movement.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The number of non-human supernatural beings believed to exist by the Taipings were

limited and included Satan (the "old serpent-Devil"), demons, Jesus, and the Holy Spirit (Bohr 2010, 375; 377). The latter two were distinguished from God by Hong Xiuquan who regarded Trinitarian belief as a dilution of true monotheism. Accordingly, he declared Jesus to be God's son only (Bohr 2010, 389-90). Consequently, Hong denied Jesus' divinity while still seeming to regard him in a class apart from other humans (Bohr 2006, 112).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: This seems to be the case only in dreams as the only instance in which supernatural beings are described as being seen is Hong Xiuquan's dream sequence of 1837 (Bohr 2006, 99-100).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Though tentative, it seems reasonable to suppose that this would have been limited to the mediums hosting the Heavenly Father and Jesus during their descents into the Guangxi hills.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Divided into good and evil

Notes: Supernatural beings in Taiping belief are divided into those that are good and of God (Jesus and the Holy Spirit) and those that are evil (Satan and demons).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: This question is difficult to answer and is answered "yes" only with reference to the leader of the Taiping movement, Hong Xiuquan, whose nature is relatively ambiguous. Hong was the self-proclaimed younger brother of Jesus (and thus son of God, the Heavenly Father) and the messianic founder of the Taipings who was declared a "Heavenly King" (tianwang 天王) by the Heavenly Father and charged, in a dream, with returning China to its monotheistic past (Bohr 2010, 372). However, Hong later denied his own divinity and, instead, declared himself to be the reincarnation of Melchizedek, the messianic founder of Jerusalem and to have had advanced knowledge of Jesus' birth and the Heavenly Father's descents into the Guangxi hills (Bohr 2010, 372-373). These points would seem to set Hong Xiuquan apart from ordinary humans without necessarily rendering him divine and so this question is answered "yes" with the understanding that Hong was not considered literally divine despite his elevated and salvific status.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Hong Xiuquan, at times, claimed that he had greater powers of knowledge than an ordinary person, though it is not clear how consistent such claims were. Moreover, how seriously one takes such claims depends on one's own beliefs regarding Hong's status. Therefore, the subsequent questions are answered as "I don't know."

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– I don't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Hong Xiquan was the younger brother of Jesus and the reincarnation of Melchizedek, the messianic founder of Jerusalem

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

Notes: Hong Xiuquan was himself a monarch.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping movement divided supernatural beings into good and evil. God was considered the only true deity and was purely good. The Taipings rejected the doctrine of Trinitarianism and so declared that Jesus was not divine, despite his status as God's eldest son. They also believed in the Holy Spirit, though it is unclear what this meant given their rejection of Trinitarianism (Bohr 2006, 112). Evil supernatural beings included Satan (the "old serpent-Devil") and demons (Bohr 2010, 377).

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus was considered God's eldest son. As described elsewhere in this entry, Hong Xiuquan was also considered God's son and Jesus' younger brother.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: God, the Heavenly Father, was the supreme ruler of the cosmos, with all other beings below him.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– I don't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: God, the Heavenly Father, is omniscient and judges the behaviour, thoughts, and sins of all people.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: It is important to mention that, although murder was considered a sin, the same prohibition did not apply to killing others in battle in support of the Taiping movement's millenarian aspirations.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: It is important to mention that, although murder was considered a sin, the same prohibition did not apply to killing others in battle in support of the Taiping movement's millenarian aspirations.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping movement mandated heterosexual monogamy (in the form of marriage) for both men and women, though they did allow remarriage (Bohr 2010, 384). This applied, however, to only the rank and file. Hong Xiuquan and his fellow kings maintained harems, due in part to their long history in Chinese practice and parallels with practices in Old Jerusalem (Bohr 2016, 114).

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Licentiousness

Notes: Beyond the basic requirement of monogamous marriage, the Taiping movement was also deeply concerned about licentiousness, which was considered sinful, and required that men and women live apart from one another in separate camps so as to encourage probity (Bohr 2006, 111). They also banned practices such as prostitution (Bohr 2006, 113).

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Achieving the success of the Taiping Tianguo

Notes: Because the Heavenly Father had charged the Taiping movement with restoring China to a its primordial golden age, the success or failure of this endeavour (as well as a person's contributions to it) were naturally matters of importance in the context of supernatural monitoring.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife is understood as a consequence of sin and of losing faith in God, as well as not following God's commands in one's lifetime.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife is understood as a consequence of sin and of losing faith in God, as well as not following God's commands in one's lifetime.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: A soul punished in the afterlife would reside in Hell, a place of eternal torment.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Although divine punishment of sin was generally understood to occur in the afterlife, there were instances in which punishment was thought to be meted out in the living world. Chief among these was the Taiping movement itself, which was understood as the instrument of God's wrath in punishing Chinese apostasy. The Taiping movement was thus understood as one of the five instances in which the Heavenly Father had descended to Earth in "great anger." The other instances were "the Old Testament Flood and Exodus, Jesus' ministry, and Hong [Xiuquan]'s vision" (Bohr 2006, 112).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: A soul rewarded in the afterlife would reside in Heaven, a paradise of eternal joy.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Although rewards on the mortal world were not emphasized by the Taiping movement, the utopian state that it sought to create was meant to be a counterpart to Heaven and so reward the faithful during their mortal lifetimes.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The Taipings were a millenarian movement that regard Hong Xiuquan as a messianic figure chosen by God to overthrow the apostate Manchu regime of the Qing and restore China to its pre-Confucian and monotheistic golden age. Accordingly, the Taipings considered themselves to be living during a time of millenarian and messianic salvation and as participating in the work of restoring China's golden age (Bohr 2010, 372).

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Whether or not the Taiping vision can be said to include an "eschatology" is difficult to answer because its focus was on the transformation of China in particular and not the entire world. However, this goal was understood as part of a larger effort to bring about a new world order under the rulership of the Heavenly Father (Bohr 2006, 105). Hong Xiuquan even suggested that, within this new world order, China would reign supreme over other nations (Bohr 2006, 112). Given these points, it seems reasonable to regard the Taipings' utopian vision as at least partially eschatological in nature.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Because the Taipings considered contemporary China to have fallen from a past golden age (and to be therefore apostate), they drew a sharp distinction between their moral code based on the Heavenly Father's Ten Commandments and the existing norms and morals of the Qing dynasty (Bohr 2010, 376-377). Their goal was to turn the inhabitants of the Qing away from the dynasty's degraded, apostate norms and return them to the true morality of the Heavenly Father.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Although Taiping morality can be read in virtuous terms (such as filial piety, loyalty, courage, and devotion), it was not understood that way by the Taiping themselves but rather as following the Ten Commandments of God as reinterpreted through Hong Xiuquan (Bohr 2010, 380). Accordingly, this question is answered "yes" simply to detail some of the traits of Taiping behaviour.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Universal love was a crucial ideal for the Taiping movement.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– No

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– No

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– No

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping movement mandated heterosexual monogamy (in the form of marriage) for both men and women, though they did allow remarriage (Bohr 2010, 384). This applied, however, to only

the rank and file. Hong Xiuquan and his fellow kings maintained harems, due in part to their long history in Chinese practice and parallels with practices in Old Jerusalem (Bohr 2016, 114). Beyond the basic requirement of monogamous marriage, the Taiping movement was also deeply concerned about licentiousness and required that men and women live apart from one another in separate camps so as to encourage probity (Bohr 2006, 111).

↳ Monogamy (males):
– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):
– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):
– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):
– No

Notes: The Taiping movement is notable for its high degree of equality between men and women and for banning a variety of practices termed "female servitude," many of which were sexual in nature. Women were encouraged to marry and remarry of their own accord, and Hong Xiuquan abolished "footbinding, arranged marriage, polygamy, wife purchase, dowries, widow suicide, and prostitution" (Bohr 2006, 113; Bohr 2010, 384). As well, Hong decreed that anyone caught violating a woman during Taiping conquests was to be executed (Bohr 2006, 114). For more on non-sexual rules of male-female equality see the introduction to this entry and the notes below under "Society and Institutions."

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping movement banned opium smoking, tobacco smoking, and alcohol, all of which were considered to be sins against the individual and signs of China's decline into decadence from a primordial state of Christian utopia (Bohr 2006, 108).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: A key feature of the Taiping movement was the "Sacred Treasury," a form of property-sharing inspired by Hakka practice. Members would contribute their possessions, including their homes, to this communal fund, which was then used by Hong Xiuquan to support the community as a whole. In Guangxi, this fund was used to support people during famines and natural disasters (Bohr 2006, 108-109). This practice continued even after the Taipings conquered Nanjing. Citizens were required to turn over their private property to the "Sacred Treasury," and soldiers were required to surrender any loot they obtained (Bohr 2010, 384; Bohr 2006, 111).

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Sacred Treasury

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the ritual observances described elsewhere in this section, the theocratic nature of the Taiping movement and its requirements of military and public service meant that those within it essentially devoted all their time to the religious group.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Recruitment into the Taiping movement, particularly once it moved out of Thistle Mountain on its millenarian crusade, required participation in the movement's armies. Failure to perform courageously in battle was punished by execution in the form of either beheading or dismemberment (Bohr 2006, 113).

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: For example, members would say grace before meals (Bohr 2010, 380).

↳

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Although the Taipings did not celebrate important Christian festivals such as Easter and Christmas, they did maintain very important ceremonies such as funerals, baptisms, weddings, and Sabbath worship (Bohr 2010, 390; Bohr 2006, 113). Many of these grew more elaborate over time, Sabbath worship, which came to include the recitation of the doxology over "an altar of three bowls each of tea, meat, rice, and vegetables," in addition to sermons (Bohr 2006, 113).

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Yes
Notes: For example, corporate worship on Thistle Mountain included the singing of Christian hymns accompanied by "Chinese gongs, drums, and cymbals" (Bohr 2010, 379) and Sabbath worship after the Taipings became established in Nanjing included hymns, incense, and fireworks (Bohr 2006, 113).

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Taipings referred to one another as "brother" and "sister." This was a Baptist custom shared by the Hakka, the "ethnic" group that formed the core of the Taiping movement (Bohr 2006, 108).

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The Taiping movement operated during the Qing dynasty (1644-1912 CE), which was created when the Manchu conquered the Ming empire and which was one of the largest empires in world history. The Taiping movement created a theocratic empire (ruled by Hong Xiuquan as monarch) inside the Qing empire that, at its height, included over 30,000,000 people.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: A key feature of the Taiping movement was the "Sacred Treasury," a form of property-sharing inspired by Hakka practice. Members would contribute their possessions, including their homes, to this communal fund, which was then used by Hong Xiuquan to support the community as a whole. In Guangxi, this fund was used to support people during famines and natural disasters (Bohr 2006, 108-109). This practice continued even after the Taipings conquered Nanjing. Citizens were required to turn over their private property to the "Sacred Treasury," and soldiers were required to surrender any loot they obtained (Bohr 2010, 384; Bohr 2006, 111).

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Extended kinship networks in the form of clans or lineages could, at times, provide famine relief for those within them.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: A key feature of the Taiping movement was the "Sacred Treasury," a form of property-sharing inspired by Hakka practice. Members would contribute their possessions, including their homes, to this

communal fund, which was then used by Hong Xiuquan to support the community as a whole. In Guangxi, this fund was used to support people during famines and natural disasters (Bohr 2006, 108-109). This practice continued even after the Taipings conquered Nanjing. Citizens were required to turn over their private property to the "Sacred Treasury," and soldiers were required to surrender any loot they obtained (Bohr 2010, 384; Bohr 2006, 111).

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Extended kinship networks in the form of clans or lineages could, at times, provide poverty relief for those within them.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: After their conquest of Nanjing, the Taipings organized special "institutes" (guan 官), which housed unmarried women, widows, the elderly, orphans, and the infirm (Bohr 2006, 114; Bohr 2010, 384).

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Extended kinship networks in the form of clans or lineages could, at times, provide care for the elderly and infirm within them.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Taipings instituted formal education in the areas that they conquered, aiming to establish a civil service examination based on the Taiping Bible (Bohr 2010, 384).

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The Taiping movement is notable for its egalitarian treatment of men and women. In addition to his banning of sexual practices that he considered exploitative (described elsewhere in this entry), Hong Xiuquan also mandated that women be granted full access to property ownership as well as "manual labour, education, civil service examinations, government and military service, and court nobility" (Bohr 2006, 113; Bohr 2010, 384).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: In order to manage their conquered territories, the Taiping movement utilized a bureaucracy of officials in addition to the courts of Hong Xiuquan and his brother kings. In keeping with the theocratic nature of the Taiping state, and the fact that there was no ordained clergy, these officials also officiated at "worship services, baptisms, weddings, and funerals" (Bohr 2006, 113).

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: A key feature of the Taiping movement was the "Sacred Treasury," a form of property-sharing inspired by Hakka practice. Members would contribute their possessions, including their homes, to this communal fund, which was then used by Hong Xiuquan to support the community as a whole. In Guangxi, this fund was used to support people during famines and natural disasters (Bohr 2006, 108-109). This practice continued even after the Taipings conquered Nanjing. Citizens were required to turn over their private property to the "Sacred Treasury," and soldiers were required to surrender any loot they obtained (Bohr 2010, 384; Bohr 2006, 111).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Extended kinship networks in the form of clans or lineages could provide this service.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: As a theocratic state, the Taiping Tianguo managed all public works.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Extended kinship networks in the form of clans or lineages could provide this service.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: As a theocratic state, the Taiping Tianguo managed all public works.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: In order to fund the Taiping Tianguo, the Taiping leadership imposed taxes on those living in the territories that they conquered. However, there were consistent efforts to keep these as low as possible. The Taiping attempted to implement a more egalitarian Land System, but, after Hong Xiuquan assassinated Yang Xiuqing and 20,000 members of his court in 1856, efforts to implement this system faltered and Taiping commanders relied on more traditional methods of tax collection (Bohr 2010, 385).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: As a theocratic state, the Taiping Tianguo managed all state institutions, including an institutionalized legal and enforcement system.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: As a theocratic state, the Taiping Tianguo managed all state institutions, including an institutionalized legal and enforcement system.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Taiping punishments included "beheading or dismemberment for smoking opium, cowardice in battle, failing to memorize the Ten Commandments, and hoarding private property;" execution for anyone caught violating a woman during a Taiping conquest; and "the severing of ears and noses, branding of faces, and beatings with bamboo" for lesser offenses such as tobacco smoking and neglecting religious observances (Bohr 2006, 113-114).

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: As a theocratic state, the Taiping Tianguo managed all state institutions, including an institutionalized legal and enforcement system.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: For almost the entirety of its existence, the Taiping movement was at war with the Qing empire. It was thus focused on war and its standing army, which it deployed in an attempt to overthrow the Manchu emperor and conquer the Qing. Recruitment procedures were particularly harsh as new recruits were given only three weeks to memorize the Ten Commandments and failure to do so was met with execution (Bohr 2006, 111; 113).

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: For almost the entirety of its existence, the Taiping movement was at war with the Qing empire. It was thus constantly subject to attacks by the Qing armies.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to using standard written Chinese, the Taiping movement was notable for inventing its own characters.

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– I don't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: In 1852, Feng Yunshan created a new calendar that mixed elements of solar and lunar calendars and eliminated the "fatalism of lucky and unlucky days." The intention of the calendar was to "deepen dependence on the Heavenly Father, break with the old order, and initiate the [Taiping] theocratic "Heavenly Dynasty" (Bohr 2006, 111).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: As mentioned above, the Taipings rejected the imperial calendar in favour of their own.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: As a theocratic state, the Taiping Tianguo managed all state functions, works, and services, including agriculture.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: P. Bohr Richard. Taiping 'Christianity' and Its Legacy. (R. Tiedemann G.), *Christianity in China: A Handbook*. Volume 2: 1800 to the Present. Brill.

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